

OSPARK Research Protocol Appendix 4: Study 2 Knowledge Check Pre-Test

Notes:

- *The participant information sheet, consent form, and closing message are adapted from [templates](#) provided by the Research Governance Ethics and Integrity Team at Queen's University Belfast.*
- *Each level 1 heading represents a new page in the online survey.*

Page 1: Participant information sheet and consent form

Title of study: Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK): Study 2 pre-test

Thank you for your interest in taking part in this study. Before you decide whether to participate, it is important that you understand why this research is being conducted and what it will involve. Please take the time to read the following information carefully. You may discuss it with others if needed. Please download the page if you will need it for future reference.

Please contact us if you have any questions or need further information. Our contact details are further down the page.

This content is adapted with permission from [participant information sheet and consent form templates](#) developed by the Research Governance, Ethics and Integrity Team at Queen's University Belfast.

Quick summary

- This study is being organised by researchers from OLS (Open Life Science Limited) and DRA (DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH).
- We are aiming to identify the outreach, marketing, and communications activities that open science advocates take part in; the barriers they experience regarding these activities; and their needs and preferences regarding training in these topics. We

would also like to assess how knowledgeable and confident open science advocates are about core concepts in outreach activities.

- This questionnaire is a pre-test of survey materials we will use in the main study. It involves both open and closed questions.
- Your data will be stored on the survey platform and will be accessible only to the [OLS](#) and [DRA](#) teams until data analysis begins. Anonymous data will be shared on an openly accessible GitHub and/or Zenodo repository. All data storage will be in compliance with UK data protection legislation.
- This study is part of the Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Bootcamp, funded by the first OSCARS Open Call. The OSCARS project has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101129751.

What is the purpose of the study?

Our research aims to understand open science advocates engagement, experienced barriers, and training needs in the area of outreach, marketing, and communications. As part of this, we would like to assess how knowledgeable and confident open science advocates are about core concepts in outreach activities. This questionnaire is a pre-test of a short quiz which will be part of this research.

Who can take part?

We are seeking responses from anyone who is involved in an open science initiative, project, service, or infrastructure. We expect this will mainly be researchers, research professionals, or students who are engaged in open science. We are aiming to recruit 20 people to participate in this pre-test.

What will happen to me if I take part?

This questionnaire will involve:

1. Giving informed consent;
2. Answering knowledge-based questions about outreach, marketing, and communications;
3. Providing some feedback about these questions.

We expect that this will take less than 10 minutes. The exact time will depend on how much feedback you decide to give.

What will happen to my data?

This research will be conducted in compliance with data protection legislation. Your data will be stored and managed by OLS (Open Life Science Limited), a UK based social enterprise. As part of this study, we will be collecting your anonymous survey responses. No identifiable data (such as IP addresses) will be collected.

This study has been designed according to open science principles. Anonymised data will therefore be shared publicly under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC-BY\)](#) license, unless deemed to be a risk to participant safety or wellbeing.

Our full data management plan [<add link when available>](#) is publicly accessible.

What are the possible benefits, risks, or disadvantages of taking part?

The benefit of taking part in this study is having the opportunity to shape research on outreach, marketing, and communications for open science initiatives.

There is a risk that your responses may be identifiable, despite anonymity, as there are some open text boxes. To mitigate this, the researchers will check open text responses and anonymise any potentially identifiable information.

What if something goes wrong?

If you have any concerns about any aspects of the study, you should contact the lead researcher:

Bethan Iley
OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager
bethan@we-are-ols.org

Should you remain unhappy with the response and wish to make a formal complaint, please make a report under OLS's [Code of Conduct policy](#).

What will happen to the results of the research?

Upon conclusion of this study, the findings may be written into a scientific journal article and presented at scientific conferences. This is to share our results with other researchers in the field. You can get updated about the findings of this research by signing up to the [OSPARK mailing list](#).

The anonymous data from this study will be shared publicly under a [Creative Commons Attribution \(CC-BY\) 4.0 International license](#). This means that other researchers may use the

data to verify our results or conduct their own research in the future.

Who is organising and funding the research?

This study is led by a team of researchers at OLS (Open Life Science Limited) and DRA (DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH). OLS is a non-profit company limited by guarantee, based in the United Kingdom (company number [12824090](#)). DRA is a grassroots trainer network based in Germany (HRB 295646).

The research team for this study consists of the following people:

- Bethan Iley, OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager, OLS
- Heidi Seibold, Co-Executive Director, DRA
- Joyce Kao, Co-Executive Director, DRA
- Yo Yehudi, Co-Executive Director, OLS

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Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed by *<name of research ethics committee or IRB>*. If you have any questions or concerns about the ethics review for this study, you can contact them at *<IRB email>* using reference *<reference number>*.

Contact for Further Information

If you have questions or comments about the study, please contact the lead researcher on this study:

Bethan Iley
OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager
bethan@we-are-ols.org

If your questions or concerns remain unresolved, please contact the Principle Investigator:

Yo Yehudi
Executive Director

yo@we-are-ols.org

Thank you for your interest in this study and for taking the time to read through this information page.

Please indicate you understand and consent to taking part in this research using the checkboxes below.

- I confirm that I have read, or had read to me, and understand the information presented above about this study. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and these have been answered fully.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason and without my legal rights being affected.
- I understand the study is being conducted by researchers from Open Life Science Limited and that my personal information will be held and handled in compliance with data protection legislation.
- I understand that data collected as part of this will be accessible to employees and contractors at Open Life Science Limited (also known as OLS) and DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH (also known as DRA). I give permission for these individuals to have access to this information.
- I understand that the information I provide may be published as a report. Anonymity will be maintained and it will not be possible to identify me from any publications.
- I agree that my anonymous survey responses can be deposited in repositories such as GitHub and/or Zenodo to promote transparency and public accessibility to research.
- I agree to take part in the above study.

Page 2: Knowledge

The OSPARK-aligned answer is highlighted in light green.

You will now be shown a series of 9 questions about outreach strategy. In the full research project, these questions will assess whether someone's strategy aligns with OSPARK's course content.

For each question, please answer as though you were taking the full survey, then provide your feedback about the question.

Page 3: Question 1

Who might be in the target market for an open science initiative?

- Students
- Researchers in academia
- Researchers in industry, the public sector, or nonprofit organisations
- Research professionals and support staff, such as lab managers and librarians
- University administrators
- All of the above
- I'm not sure

How clear is the meaning of this question? *Note: Rated on a 4-point Likert scale: very clear (1), slightly clear (2), slightly unclear (3), very unclear (4), I'm not sure (N/A).*

Why have you given this rating?

Do you have any other feedback or suggestions about this question?

Page 4: Question 2

Conference talks and networking sessions are a form of marketing for your open science initiative.

- True
- False
- I'm not sure

How clear is the meaning of this question? *Note: Rated on a 4-point Likert scale: very clear (1), slightly clear (2), slightly unclear (3), very unclear (4), I'm not sure (N/A).*

Why have you given this rating?

Do you have any other feedback or suggestions about this question?

Page 5: Question 3

Which communications channel should you use to advertise your open science initiative?

- The ones with the most overall users
- The ones frequently used by the people I want to reach
- The ones which are easily accessible through my job
- I'm not sure

How clear is the meaning of this question? *Note: Rated on a 4-point Likert scale: very clear (1), slightly clear (2), slightly unclear (3), very unclear (4), I'm not sure (N/A).*

Why have you given this rating?

Do you have any other feedback or suggestions about this question?

Page 6: Question 4

What is the most effective strategy to grow your open science initiative's social media page?

- Occasionally commenting on and sharing other initiatives' work
- Spending 1 hour per day "liking" every post on the account's timeline
- Using 20+ hashtags in every post, on every platform
- I'm not sure

How clear is the meaning of this question? *Note: Rated on a 4-point Likert scale: very clear (1), slightly clear (2), slightly unclear (3), very unclear (4), I'm not sure (N/A).*

Why have you given this rating?

Do you have any other feedback or suggestions about this question?

Page 7: Question 5

What is most important in a talk about your open science initiative?

- Providing clear information about the initiative
- Connecting emotionally with the audience
- Both are equally important
- I'm not sure

How clear is the meaning of this question? *Note: Rated on a 4-point Likert scale: very clear (1), slightly clear (2), slightly unclear (3), very unclear (4), I'm not sure (N/A).*

Why have you given this rating?

Do you have any other feedback or suggestions about this question?

Page 8: Question 6

What is the main benefit of short vertical videos, such as TikToks or YouTube Shorts, over long-form videos?

- There is often better discoverability through wider algorithmic reach
- Viewers are more likely to look at your profile and other content
- It's easier to establish a connection with the audience
- I'm not sure

How clear is the meaning of this question? *Note: Rated on a 4-point Likert scale: very clear (1), slightly clear (2), slightly unclear (3), very unclear (4), I'm not sure (N/A).*

Why have you given this rating?

Do you have any other feedback or suggestions about this question?

Page 9: Question 7

Marketing and communications are primarily about...

- Promoting your open science initiative
- Providing value to your audience
- I'm not sure

How clear is the meaning of this question? *Note: Rated on a 4-point Likert scale: very clear (1), slightly clear (2), slightly unclear (3), very unclear (4), I'm not sure (N/A).*

Why have you given this rating?

Do you have any other feedback or suggestions about this question?

Page 10: Question 8

Interacting with similar or competing open science initiatives is harmful to your open science initiative's marketing and communications goals.

- True
- False
- I'm not sure

How clear is the meaning of this question? *Note: Rated on a 4-point Likert scale: very clear (1), slightly clear (2), slightly unclear (3), very unclear (4), I'm not sure (N/A).*

Why have you given this rating?

Do you have any other feedback or suggestions about this question?

Page 11: Question 9

What would normally be included in a marketing and communications strategy plan?

- Broad guidance about the goals, style, tone, and channels you will use
- Specific step-by-step instructions on how to create each social media post
- I'm not sure

How clear is the meaning of this question? *Note: Rated on a 4-point Likert scale: very clear (1), slightly clear (2), slightly unclear (3), very unclear (4), I'm not sure (N/A).*

Why have you given this rating?

Do you have any other feedback or suggestions about this question?

Page 12: End message

This will be shown as a post-submission message.

Thank you for your time and for taking part in this pre-test. Your response has been recorded.

If you have questions or comments about the study, please contact the lead researcher on this study:

Bethan Iley
OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager
bethan@we-are-ols.org

